

Assessment of phosphorylation of SMAD1 and Alk2 under different activating conditions

7th November 2018

Aim: To look at the influence of the Alk2 mutation and the type II receptor used on the rate of SMAD1 and Alk2 phosphorylation.

Setup:

Proteins were thawed from storage at -80°C and concentrations assessed by Nano drop.

From the concentrations, appropriate dilutions were calculated to get a final concentration of 40 μM for all proteins in a reaction mix of 50 μL (volume made up with water).

A 'master mix' containing ATP, ions and DTT was made up and added to activate the reaction at the start of the experiment.

Protein concentration calculation.

Protein	Extinction coeff	Absorbance	Concentration (μM)	40uM dilution in 50ul
Alk2 WT	60390	6.1	101.0101	19.8
Alk2 R206H	58900	9.26	157.2156	12.72138
Alk2 Q207E	58900	4.85	82.34295	24.28866
ACVR2	51910	21.8	419.9576	4.762385
BMPR2 (active)	46870	16.3	347.7704	5.75092
BMPR2 (kinase dead)	46870	10.97	234.0516	8.545123
SMAD1	35410	4.65	131.3188	15.23011

Master Mix

100mM stock	Vol	1 rxn	100 rxn	50 rxn
ATP	100	0.25	25	12.5
DTT	100	2.5	250	125
Mg	100	2.5	250	125
Mn	100	1	100	50
		6.25	625	312.5

Reaction setup

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
ACVR1 WT	19.8			19.8			19.8		
ACVT1 R206H		13			13			13	
ACVR1 Q207E			24			24			24
ACVR2	5	5	5						5
BMPR2 (active)				6	6	6			
BMPR2 (dead)							8.5	8.5	8.5
Master Mix	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
SMAD1	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15

Reactions were set up in a 96 well plate, the plate was spun to ensure thorough mixing before the reaction was started by the addition of 6.26 μ L of master mix. 1 μ L of reaction mixture was extracted from each experimental condition simultaneously using a 12 channel pipette and the reaction quenched with acid in 60 μ L Mass Spec running buffer (water with 0.1% formic acid).

Mass spec analysis:

Intact mass was determined using a QTOF mass spectrometer. A C3 cartridge was used for HPLC prior to ionisation.

The resulting chromatogram was used to extract the appropriate spectra corresponding to protein elution peak from the C3 column. All spectra were extracted simultaneously. Deconvolution was undertaken between 10kDa and 50kDa across a limited m/z range of 600 – 3000.

Data was exported with a peak intensity for every Dalton of the deconvoluted spectra.

Data processing:

Peak intensity for the masses corresponding to the apo and phosphorylated states of all proteins were extracted from the raw deconvoluted data using a python script written by Elliot Nelson. Up to two phosphorylation states were extracted for SMAD1. All other proteins had up to 8 phosphorylation states extracted.

Representative plot showing up to +8 phosphorylation states on the Alk2 Q207E mutant protein after 25 minutes incubated with ACVR2. This is a mix of auto and trans phosphorylation.

Previous experiments have shown that SMAD1 has two phosphorylation sites on the C terminal tail while up to 8 phosphorylations have been clearly observed for type I and II receptors. Phosphorylations beyond 8 were not observed or were so slight as to be insignificant. Previous experiments have also shown that peak height is proportional to the area under the peak so height can be used as a measurement of rate.

Peak height data was adjusted for number of phosphorylations at each phosphorylation state to get the total amount of phosphorylation. E.g. the height of the +2P state was multiplied by 2 to get the total phosphorylation contribution, the height of the +4P state was multiplied by 4 to get the total phosphorylation contribution etc.

The total phosphorylation across all phosphorylation states was then summed for each time point in order to plot the rate of overall phosphorylation.

Graphs were plotted in excel to compare the phosphorylation rates on both SMAD1 and Alk2 in various combinations to look at the influence of the Alk2 mutation or the type II receptor used on each of the outputs.

Intensity of signal is not a valid comparison between the runs as it cannot be guaranteed that the constructs fly identically in the mass spec however the initial slopes of rate of phosphorylation, the time taken for maximal phosphorylation to be reached and the overall shape of the curves are valid points of comparison.

Graphs of SMAD1 phosphorylation comparing the effect of different Alk2 forms (WT, Q207E and R206H mutations) and different type II receptors (ACVR2, BMPR2 active and BMPR2 kinase dead)

Graphs of Alk2 phosphorylation comparing the effect of different Alk2 forms (WT, Q207E and R206H mutations) and different type II receptors (ACVR2, BMPR2 active and BMPR2 kinase dead)

Conclusions:

SMAD1 phosphorylations.

SMAD1 phosphorylation by Alk2 wt + ACVR2 gives a distinctive sigmoidal pattern that has a delayed start and doesn't reach maximum until around 20 minutes.

In contrast, Alk2 mutants show much faster activation of SMAD1 with ACVR2, reaching maximum after around 5 minutes. The rate of Q207E seems to be slightly slower than R206H.

The difference between Q207E and R206H is seen much more starkly when paired with BMPR2 (active or kinase dead) where Q207E is much slower than R206H and both are faster than base rate.

Alk2 phosphorylations:

The rates of auto and trans phosphorylation of Alk2 (WT and mutants) does not seem to be effected by the type II receptor present. I.e. Alk2 WT phosphorylation is not effected by the type II used, Alk2 Q207E phosphorylation isn't effected by the type II and Alk2 R206H isn't effected by the type II.

However, the presence of the mutation in Alk2 increases the rate of phosphorylation when compared to the same type II. For all type II's, R206H had a faster rate than Q207E.

Future plans:

With the current data it's hard to quantify the readings as I don't have sufficient repeats to get any idea of error however the general trends match data previously recorded. Repeats will need to be done when I have access to more purified Alk2 WT after expression issues have been resolved.